

The role of STEAM education in curriculum 5.0

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Abstract.

At the threshold of the Fifth Industrial Revolution, as the economy shifts to more knowledge-intensive industries, there is an urgent need to develop the skills of students who are the leaders of future technological advancements and therefore redesign the curriculum. It is widely accepted that children get more motivated for learning when they choose a subject at school. Therefore, the teacher's role is to present knowledge in an attractive and interesting way. Inspiring students is crucial for the learning process. This is a difficult problem for STEM education because many primary school teachers do not necessarily have good knowledge of science. Teachers cannot inspire their students when they do not feel enthusiastic about a teaching subject. A CERN pioneering program, "Playing with protons" was created to solve this problem.

Keywords: STEM education, CERN, creativity, curriculum 5.0

Introduction

Industry 5.0 offers many opportunities for academic institutions to advance to the next level. Faculty 5.0 should go along with Curriculum 5.0. In the new curriculum we need to incorporate learning about robotics, internet of things, augmented reality, smart materials but at the same time integrate non-technical subjects (such as project management, communication, arts, etc.) in order to develop transdisciplinary skills. It is also important to focus on questions of ethics, diversity, social inclusion, and sustainability (e.g. teaching the Sustainable Development Goals).

1. STEAM education in Curriculum 5.0

In this curriculum, STEM, as a transdisciplinary approach, aims to promote research spirit, logical thinking and social skills. Recently, arts have also been incorporated into STEM teaching, making these projects even more creative and interesting. As a result, the STEM acronym is now becoming STEAM (Land, 2013). Emphasis is placed on empirical and exploratory-discovery learning, autonomy and active participation of students, through trial and errors, in a series of interactive projects that incorporate the five fields of STEAM (Maslyk, 2016). The acquisition of basic skills through STEAM projects, prepares young people for the future, as STEAM learning is framed in the daily life of young people outside the classroom (Daugherty, 2013). STEAM Education has as its center the problem solving ideas. Furthermore, STEAM education stimulates students' attention by developing their abilities for expression, creativity, with innovation playing the most significant role (Aguilera & Ortiz-Revilla, 2021).

STEAM can be unplugged or make use of technology. Unplugged activities can be implemented without the use of computers and can be used to engage in computational thinking dimensions, embedding computer science concepts into the curriculum. (Curzon, 2013). It is very important to

promote computational thinking in the classroom, which includes abstraction, algorithmic thinking, decomposition and pattern recognition (Hoyle&Noss, 2015). Computational thinking involves solving problems and designing systems, by drawing on the concepts fundamental to computer science (Wing, 2006).

Educational Technologies such as augmented/virtual reality, clickers” or key-pads”, cloud computing, and internet of me can promote STEM education, through the adoption of innovative teaching strategies, like hands-on activities, mini- and remote labs, building models, etc.

2. Teacher Training on STEAM education

Training teachers on STEAM practices is an important issue. A research was conducted in Australia among pre-service primary school teachers by a chief scientist of Australia (Prinsley, Johnston, 2015). The research investigated beliefs regarding STEM in terms of importance, innovation, skills in future, and high-quality specialist teachers to teach in primary schools and there were also questions on understanding concerning attracting high achievers to teaching, including STEM in teacher preparation, professional development, and leadership in primary schools. The questionnaire included questions about intentions to teach STEM focused on the interest connected to daily life, the ability to apply mathematics, the need for primary teachers to be supported by a specialist STEM teacher, the needs for separate subject on STEM in the university for pre-service teachers’ university programs, and the teachers’ ability in STEM to transform creativity and innovation among children. Future teachers who answered the questionnaires placed emphasis on the fact that their knowledge of science and technology was minimal. However, they had positive intentions to teach STEM since they believed that STEM-related subjects are important for life.

Among the conclusions of the study are the following:

- Pre-service teachers should have experiences in STEM in order to apply their knowledge, their skills and the principles of STEM efficiently.
- Science knowledge and sound pedagogical practices should be integrated in order for teachers to practice STEM teaching in an optimal manner.
- Ongoing professional training in STEM education is necessary for all teachers.
- STEM should include school and non-school experiences in STEM-related activities (Kurup, Li, Powell & Brown, 2019).

Teachers’ perception of knowledge, confidence, and efficacy for teaching STEM influences students’ learning and classroom practices (Nadelson et al., 2013). Teachers’ ability in integrating background knowledge of technological pedagogical content knowledge to a STEM curriculum seems a challenge to pre-service and in-service teachers (Hofer & Grandgenett, 2012). It is also essential for teachers to have a professional development education in STEM that would enable them to integrate disciplines and will provide them an understanding of teaching approaches that combine hands-on activities with the effort to develop twenty- first century competencies. Furthermore, there is a need for policies of STEM that are based on the four-dimensional framework: knowledge, skills, character, meta-learning. (Bybee, 2013).

3. Playing with Protons program and its goals

In most countries, physics is taught in high-schools, in ways that don’t motivate students and as a result they make them think that the subject is boring and useless for them. One of the reasons that in most cases science is taught only in high-schools is that there are not specialized science teachers in primary school and since modern physics can be a difficult subject, primary school teachers may lack

the confidence and knowledge to perform well in the classroom (Wilkins, 2010). In this manner, they are excluded from the creative world of the modern scientific approaches that extend the boundaries of science in a way that physics can meet philosophy and imagination (Etkina, 2015).

However, according to several studies, the public wants science to be taught early in primary education. The majority of participants in the above-mentioned studies believe that science in primary school will help students to perform well in high-school. (Belden, Lien & Nelson-Dusek, 2010)

Eshach and Fried (Eshach& Fried, 2005) posited that even very young children should be exposed to the world of science. Their assertions are as follows: 1. Children normally find pleasure in observing and contemplating nature. 2. The exposure of young students to science results in the development and adoption of a positive attitude towards it. 3. Early exposure to scientific phenomena prompts to better comprehension of the scientific terms studied formally later. 4. The utilization of scientifically informed language at an early age affects the eventual development of scientific concepts in a very positive way. 5. Children can understand scientific concepts and reason scientifically. 6. Science is an efficient means for developing scientific thinking.

"Playing with Protons" was a CERN program addressed to primary school students. This idea that the concepts of modern physics and science in general should be taught at an early age represented the added value of the program. This course was initially supported by the CMS and subsequently by the ATLAS experiments at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) within the framework of the CREATIONS EU project (CREATIONS EU project website) and after it was supported by the REINFORCE (REINFORCE EU project website) and FRONTIERS (FRONTIERS EU project website) European projects. In CREATIONS, 16 partners from 11 European countries developed creative approaches based on arts for an engaging science classroom in order to improve the skills of young people in STEM, raise student's interest and encourage science teachers to innovate. Combining science and art, partners were planning a variety of cultural events in which young people can experience an active and playful role within science and research. "Art@CMS", "Learning Science through Theater" and "Global Science Opera" were three of the programmes within the framework of the CREATIONS project. (CREATIONS EU project website).

The program focused on experiments conducted by the students themselves with everyday materials and objects and it resulted in the students becoming familiar with complicated scientific concepts as well as the latest developments in the field of particle physics research. Naturally, knowledge of modern physics should be explained to young students in a conceptual way rather than a mathematical way and a lot of hands-on activities should be utilized to provide a solid foundation to young students for a deeper understanding of scientific concepts (Alexopoulos&Nantsou, 2017).

The project was combined with training of primary teachers taking place at CERN (Trimoulla, 2016). Ten teachers from Greece and UK were selected in order to participate in the training program that took place at CERN's facilities. They experimented with simple materials and when they returned to their countries they diffused the knowledge they acquired to their colleagues and to their students. The main goals of the program were to enable primary school teachers to:

- Invent innovative scenarios and lesson plans to motivate their students and enrich the curriculum at the same time.
- Experience technology, science and innovation at CERN, which is the largest particle physics laboratory in the world.
- Get acquainted with new teaching approaches based on hands-on activities and experiments.
- Diffuse the knowledge they acquired at CERN to their colleagues, peers and local communities.
- Feel confident when teaching science.

"Playing with Protons" enabled primary teachers to improve their knowledge and teaching practices with creative methods that can attract the attention and get students engaged with science and technology ideas. The visit to CERN enabled teachers to transmit first-hand knowledge to students. Experiential learning for teachers ensures experiential learning for students. This is one of the most effective ways to attract the attention of students and to stimulate them. Furthermore, teachers became part of the scientific community and in this way they could transmit the values of collaboration towards common goals that furthered the progress of human civilization. All the above ensured that students would have a high-quality education experience when they participated in a CERN project.

"Playing with Protons" included continuing professional development (CPD) courses for primary school teachers, the development of learning resources and communities of interest, and continuous support for schools especially those in remote locations and schools with students who were members of relatively underprivileged communities. (CERN website).

The program allowed primary school teachers, specialists in science education and researchers working at CERN to cooperate in order to create new and original approaches that would increase the level of engagement in natural sciences, experimentation and innovation in primary school students. In particular, primary school teachers visited CERN experimental facilities to witness the one of a kind culture of the latest scientific discoveries, state-of-the-art technology and innovation at the largest particle physics laboratory on the planet. They drew inspiration and they became very eager to share the knowledge they have just discovered with peers, students, parents and the larger community. They experimented with new teaching activities focusing on hands-on activities using simple materials to increase their engagement level. Furthermore, they used innovative methods for the development of new educational scenarios and lesson plans that would make the teaching and learning process of physics more engaging and effective (Alexopoulos & Nantsou, 2017).

As a Flexible zone teacher in three Primary schools of Artemida, Athens, I had the opportunity to participate in the program "Playing with Protons". Considering that the main challenge of the program is to cultivate science, motivation and creativity in primary school students, throughout the program, students in nearly all primary school grades were involved in various creative activities. In particular, students performed artistic activities, constructions and general explorations of objects. They simulated physics experiments, they created collages and digital presentations for natural scientists. In addition, they depicted the CMS detector in multiple ways, using a variety of materials and techniques, including wood, collages, Lego, three-dimensional printing, and organizing an art exhibition at CMS, etc.

4. Selected lesson plan

4.1. Session 1 (powerpoint presentation & videos): Learn about CERN underground facilities. Engineering challenge: Create and build models and maquettes of CERN premises.

Session 2 (powerpoint presentation & videos): Learn about the CMS experiment and the science behind the experiment. Engineering challenge: Simulation of the CMS experiment.

Session 3 (powerpoint presentation & videos): The ATLAS and CMS detectors (learn the physics and engineering of the detectors). Engineering challenge: Construct models of a particle detector, like ATLAS and CMS) (with the use of everyday materials).

4.2. Scientific model

Phase 1: QUESTION: students investigate a scientifically oriented question

Balance and navigation through dialogue aid teachers and students in creatively navigating educational tensions. Ethics and trusteeship are an important consideration in experimental design and collaborative work, as well as in the initial choice of question.

Phase 2: EVIDENCE: students give priority to evidence

Risk, immersion and play are crucial in empowering pupils to generate, question and discuss.

Phase 3: ANALYSE: students analyze evidence

Students analyze evidence, using dialogue with each other and the teacher to support their developing understanding.

Phase 4: EXPLAIN: students formulate an explanation based on evidence

Students use evidence they have generated and analyzed to consider possibilities for explanations that are original to them. They use argumentation and dialogue.

Phase 5: CONNECT: students connect explanations to scientific knowledge

Students connect their explanations with scientific knowledge, using different ways of thinking and knowing ("knowing that", "knowing how", and "knowing this").

Phase 6: COMMUNICATE: students communicate and justify explanation

Communication of possibilities, ideas and justifications through dialogue with other students.

Phase 7: REFLECT: students reflect on the inquiry process and their learning

Individual, collaborative and community-based reflective activities consolidate learning and enable students and teachers.

4.3 Sessions

School: 4th Primary School of Artemida, Greece, Athens

Grades: 1st-6th grades of Primary education

SESSION 1

The Maquette of CERN's installations (construction, artistic representation)

Duration: 4 lessons X 45': 3h

Objectives

-Learn about CERN underground facilities.

-Engineering challenge: Create and build models and maquettes of CERN premises.

SESSION 2

Simulation of the CMS experiment with Led Flash Circuit and Led Chaser Circuit

Duration: 4 lessons x 45: 3h

Objectives

-Learn about the CMS experiment and the science behind the experiment.

-Engineering challenge: Simulation of the CMS experiment.

SESSION 3

Models of a particle detector (CMS and ATLAS)

Duration: 13h30 approximately

Objectives

-The detectors CMS and ATLAS (learn the physics and engineering of the detectors)

-Construct models of a particle detector (CMS and ATLAS), [use of everyday materials].

SESSION 1 Themaquette of CERN's installations (constructions, artistic representations)

SESSION 2 [Simulation of the CMS experiment with Led Flash Circuit and Led Chaser Circuit](#)

SESSION 3 1. Miniatures of the CMS detector using Lego 2. Wooden representations of the CMS detector 3. a) Paintings about the CMS Detector and Art@CMS Exhibition b) art@CMS. A virtual Gallery-A collection of the best paintings at the art@CMS (CERN) of Michael Hoch, Lindsay Olson, Paco Falco, Chris Henschke, Xavier Cortada, Alison Gill made with the digital tool artsteps. c. The CMS detector was represented in collages (materials such as jewelry, drinking straws, pills, toothpicks, bottle caps and pasta were used). d. Collage of the particle detector CMS using the app Hp Reveal of the Augmented Reality on mobile and tablet. 4. 3D printing models of CERN (the process of printing and assembling the CMS detector lasted 100 hours. Additionally, 100 hours were required for printing the "Globe of science and innovation" and 2 hours for printing and assembling of little models of Higgs bosons). 5. The particle detector CMS dessert (a dessert consisting of butter, chocolate and sugar and weighing three kilograms). 6. "Playing with Particles", Applications for web and portable devices (cross-platform, Android - IOS) "Detecting particles" (CMS, CERN) (30minutes) Level 1&Level 2. It's a part of a complete course (26 applications) on particle physics using Flashcards and Games created with the Cram Web application. In particular, the theory is presented in six thematic units (13 applications) followed by exercises in the form of quizzes, created with the Quizglobal tool, that test and enhance the understanding of the theory (13 applications). 7. Models and Artistic representations of the particle detector ATLAS (CERN) with arts and crafts and using the technique "shadow and light". 8. Models of the Particle Detector CMS (CERN) created by the students made with the digital tool Powtoon. 9. Article on Wikipedia about the CMS experiment. 10. Poems about CERN set to music and visualized (inspired by astrophysics and particle physics). The Freinet technique was used for the creation of small books.

5. Challenges-Difficulties

The main challenge I had to face was related to the Greek curriculum which does not include modern physics. I had to redesign the syllabus and be innovative and creative. I used materials that motivated my students' creativity, such as Lego, clay, cardboards, etc. My teaching style is creative and innovative. This is the reason why I promoted STEAM literacy in primary students by encouraging them to become out-of-the-box thinkers and creators. Another challenge was that I should teach particle physics to very young children therefore I had to come up with activities suitable for their age and interests. New technologies, such as 3D printers, made a significant contribution. Children were very enthusiastic about science. A great outcome of the above-mentioned activities was the production of original audio-visual and digital material in the form of educational resources about

physics and, in particular, particle physics, in collaboration with my students. I think this is a valuable material for a wide range of people. In addition, the context in which I taught the program is a public primary school in an eastern suburb of Athens. The building and the infrastructure are in terrible condition, which made my efforts even more difficult. In addition, I had to deal with underprivileged children of low socio-economic and educational status.

6. Evaluation of the program

The follow-up evaluation showed that teachers experienced higher science teaching confidence, higher interest in physics and science in general and increased creativity. A great majority of teachers agreed that they implemented their knowledge and shared it with their peers. (Alexopoulos et al, 2018). The quantitative and qualitative data of tools including questionnaires and student interviews verified the positive acceptance of the program by both the students and the teachers who participated in it as well as by the parents. The contribution of the program to the connection of school knowledge with the needs, age, level and interests of students as well as real social situations was considered to be particularly valuable. Moreover, in this context, the creation of better relationships with all students and especially those with particular learning, cultural and linguistic needs was promoted. In addition, the "Playing with Protons" gave students the opportunity to develop general skills including collaboration, communication, creativity, problem-solving and presentation. Cross-curricular and creative activities broke cultural stereotypes associated with science and scientists and demonstrated the value of learning modern physics and science at an early age. In addition, teachers and students developed initiative actions, cultivated critical and creative thinking through methodologies related to a holistic and interdisciplinary approach to knowledge and the implementation of activities and projects at individual and group level which increased students' aspirations for science-related careers. The educational climate of the schools that implemented the program was positively influenced and this contributed to the promotion of creative cooperation between all involved in the educational process. Students were open and responsive to new and diverse perspectives, they demonstrated originality and inventiveness in work, higher order thinking and problem-solving skills and they elaborated original ideas to improve and maximize creative efforts.

Conclusions

The teaching implementations of the innovative "Playing with protons" program described above have provided students with a variety of opportunities to unravel their latent capabilities and broaden the perspectives through which they perceive the world and science. Designed teaching practices have mainly contributed to the students experimenting, identifying and discovering their strong and weak intelligences, inclinations and talents. At the same time, the use of appropriate digital tools has created the prerequisites for more efficient performance by students during the learning process, since the teaching work tailored to their individual profiles has led to the creative production of works along with the acquisition of self-regulating learning and autonomy skills as well as cooperation and communication. In conclusion, the implementation of the "Playing with Protons" program in primary education could be considered as contributing to the reforming of the teaching approach of various cognitive subjects, to the creation of a multipurpose, experiential learning environment, to the design of rich, polymorphic and multimodal courses and activities and to the selection of flexible techniques and strategies. Through the philosophy on which this innovative program was based, the students became more open towards science and society and the role of the teacher was upgraded, which is the most important factor for the success of any improvement in the education system.

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